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A complex two-dimensional first integral of magnetohydrodynamics equations

J. I. H. Lopez¹† and R. A. T. Codorniu²

¹Department of Mechanics, Mackenzie Presbyterian University, Consolação, 930, Cep 01302-907, SP, BRAZIL

²Department of Automatic Control, University of Santiago de Cuba, Av. de Las Americas, CUBA

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The purpose of this article is to study some question related to the complex two-dimensional first integral equations of magnetohydrodynamics (FI-MHD). Most of the questions that we investigated are related to the transformations of differential magnetohydrodynamics operators from the real plane (\mathbb{R}) to the complex plane (\mathbb{C}). A new type of complete set of field equations appears: the first integral complex MHD equations. We also calculated a special case of complex solution for these FI-CMHD equations. In this family, with many members of coupling solutions the magnetic field appears with the same structure as the velocity field.

1. Introduction

Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) is a phenomenon where the velocity field \mathbf{u} and magnetic field \mathbf{B} are coupled. MHD is used to study the dynamics of electrically conducting fluids (Davison 2001). It establishes a coupling between the Navier-Stokes equations for fluid dynamics and Maxwell's equations for electromagnetism. Magnetic fields can induce currents in moving conductive, electrically conducting and non-magnetic fluid: liquid metals, hot ionized gases (plasmas), which in turn create forces on the fluid and influence the magnetic field itself. Magnetic fields are used to pump, stir, levitate and heat liquid metals. The earth's magnetic field, which protect the surface from radiation, is generated by the motion of the earth's liquid core. The solar magnetic field generates solar flares and sunspots, and the galactic magnetic field influences the formation of stars.

The electromagnetic part of MHD, namely Maxwell's equations, the transport equation for the magnetic field \mathbf{B} , coupled with the Navier-Stokes equations -the continuity and motion equation- form the Magnetohydrodynamic equations, along with the assumptions of Newtonian fluids and incompressibility. The coupling between the two fields ($\mathbf{u} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{B}$) happens because of the presence of a velocity field \mathbf{u} in the induction equation and the presence of the Lorentz force in the Navier-Stokes equations.

The first integrals, a non-constant function in which its derivatives vanish in the solution curves of the system, play crucial roles in studies of dynamical systems and other kinds of systems (Man 1994). First integrals help to define the problem. These values are constants that have physical significance. In many systems, they are the only computable measurements of the efficiency of the numerical methods. Monitoring or computing the first integral permit us assess the quality of the approximation, when we do not know the exact solution. The work of Scholle (Scholle *et al.* 2010) stated that for two dimensions

† Email address for correspondence: jihlopez@mackenzie.com.br

(\mathbb{R}^2) the first integral of Navier-Stokes' equations could be represented in the complex plane (\mathbb{C}). Here, in this work, we use the same procedure for MHD equations.

In this work we examine the complex plane in a first integral of MHD equations with the aid of a complex solution. The resulting equations are solved for special case of decoupling. Section 2 includes the MHD equations. Subsection 2.1 contains the complex transformations. In section 3 a family of complex coupled solutions are founded. Conclusions are drawn in section 4.

2. Non-dimensional form of the (MHD) equations

The non-dimensional form of steady and two-dimensional Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) equations describe the macroscopic state of the viscous incompressible and resistive fluid (Sermange & Temam 1983):

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} - \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \nabla p + S \nabla \left(\frac{B^2}{2} \right) - S (\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{B} &= f, \\ (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{B} - (\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} - \frac{1}{R_m} \nabla^2 \mathbf{B} &= 0, \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0, \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.1)$$

where $\rho = 1$ density of the fluid, p is the pressure, u is the velocity of the fluid particle at point x , B is the magnetic field at point x , f is the non-dimensional volume density forces. Re is a Reynolds number and \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{u} , p are non-dimensional quantities. R_m is magnetic Reynolds number, and the interaction parameter $S = \frac{M^2}{Re R_m}$, where M is the Hartman number.

2.1. Complex formulation

MHD equations can be transformed by the following complex variables (Scholle *et al.* 2010): $z := \frac{1}{2}(y+ix)$ and $\bar{z} := \frac{1}{2}(y-ix)$. The complex velocity field and magnetic field are: $u := u_x + iu_y$, $B := B_x + iB_y$. Then if multiplying the second equation for the velocity field and for the magnetic field by imaginary identity i , and sum the corresponding equations, the complex operator ∇ will satisfy the following properties:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y &= z + \bar{z}, \\ x &= \frac{1}{i}(z - \bar{z}), \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial(z + \bar{z})} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}} \right), \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} &= \frac{i \partial}{\partial(z - \bar{z})} = \frac{i}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}} \right), \\ \nabla &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} = i \frac{\partial}{\partial z}, \\ \bar{\nabla} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} = i \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.2)$$

then for all the gradients that participate in the equations (Spiegel 1972):

$$-\nabla p = - \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \right) = -i \frac{\partial p}{\partial z}, \quad (2.3)$$

for the divergences:

$$\operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u}) = \Re(\bar{\nabla}\mathbf{u}) = \Im(i\bar{\nabla}\mathbf{u}) = \Im\left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{u}}{\partial\bar{z}}\right), \quad (2.4)$$

and for the laplacians:

$$\nabla \cdot \nabla \equiv \nabla^2 = \Re(\bar{\nabla}\nabla) = \Im(i\bar{\nabla}\nabla) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial\bar{z}\partial z}, \quad (2.5)$$

The convective term is the darkest of all:

$$(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} = \nabla\left(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{u}\right) - (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}) \times \mathbf{u}, \quad (2.6)$$

because the Lamb vector $(\nabla \times \mathbf{u}) \times \mathbf{u} = \omega \times \mathbf{u}$ appears here. It is known that the kinematic identity for the Lamb vector is (Liu *et al.* 2014):

$$\omega \times \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u} - \frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{u})I = \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial\mathbf{u}^2}{\partial\bar{z}} - i \frac{\partial(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{u})}{\partial z} + i \frac{\partial(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{u})}{\partial z}, \quad (2.7)$$

which enables the convective term to be translated into complex plane. I is the unit tensor. By mathematical manipulation the following transformations are obtained:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &\mapsto \Im\left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{u}}{\partial\bar{z}}\right), \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &\mapsto \Im\left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{B}}{\partial\bar{z}}\right), \\ (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} &\mapsto i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{u}\right) - i \frac{\partial}{\partial\bar{z}} \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{u}^2\right), \\ \frac{1}{Re}\nabla^2\mathbf{u} &\mapsto \frac{1}{Re} \frac{\partial^2\mathbf{u}}{\partial\bar{z}\partial z}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.8)$$

if we take $f = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} \frac{\partial U}{\partial y}\right)^T$, then all the other terms have similar structure, which allows us to transform them without any problem:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \nabla(p + S\frac{B^2}{2} + U) &\mapsto i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (p + S\frac{B^2}{2} + U), \\ S(\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{B} &\mapsto iS \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{B}\right) - Si \frac{\partial}{\partial\bar{z}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{B}^2}{2}\right), \\ \frac{1}{Rm}\nabla^2\mathbf{B} &\mapsto \frac{1}{Rm} \frac{\partial^2\mathbf{B}}{\partial\bar{z}\partial z}, \\ (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{B} &\mapsto i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{B}\right) - i \frac{\partial}{\partial\bar{z}} \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{u}\mathbf{B}\right), \\ (\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} &\mapsto i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}\right) - i \frac{\partial}{\partial\bar{z}} \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}\right), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.9)$$

from (2.9) the complex non-integrable equations appear:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (p + \frac{\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{u}}{2} + \frac{S}{2}\bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{B} + \frac{SB^2}{2} + U) - \frac{i\partial}{2\partial\bar{z}} (\mathbf{u}^2 + S\mathbf{B}^2) &= \frac{1}{Re} \frac{\partial^2\mathbf{u}}{\partial\bar{z}\partial z}, \\ i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{B} - \frac{1}{2}\bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u}\right) - i \frac{\partial}{2\partial\bar{z}} (\mathbf{u}\mathbf{B} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}) &= \frac{1}{Rm} \frac{\partial^2\mathbf{B}}{\partial\bar{z}\partial z}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.10)$$

Here we have a problem: how to turn (2.10) into an integrable form? The two second derivatives of potentials, $\Phi(z, \bar{z})$ and $\Theta(z, \bar{z})$, permit (2.10) to resolve this problem (see a complete procedure to make a system of this type into an integrable, and to proved the existence of the potential $\Phi(z, \bar{z})$: (Scholle *et al.* 2010)). With an similar procedure the

4

J. I. H. Lopez, R. A. T. Codorniu

potential $\Theta(z, \bar{z})$ appears and plays the same role in the integrability of magnetic parcel of MHD equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \left(p + \frac{\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{u}}{2} + S(\bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{B}) + U \right) &= \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \bar{z} \partial z}, \\ \left(\frac{1}{2} \bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{B} - \frac{1}{2} \bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{u} \right) &= \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial \bar{z} \partial z}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.11)$$

the pressure is obtained from the first equation of (2.11):

$$p + \frac{\bar{\mathbf{u}}\mathbf{u}}{2} + S(\bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{B}) + U = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \bar{z} \partial z}, \quad (2.12)$$

and is entirely dependent on their status of Lagrange multiplier, see equation (2.12). That is, when substituting (2.11) with (2.10), as a result we obtain:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} i \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} - \frac{i}{2} (\mathbf{u}^2 + S\mathbf{B}^2) &= \frac{1}{Re} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial z}, \\ i \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial z^2} - i(\mathbf{u}\mathbf{B}) &= \frac{1}{Rm} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial z}, \\ \Im \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \bar{z}} \right) &= 0, \\ \Im \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \bar{z}} \right) &= 0, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.13)$$

(2.13) is the first integral of magnetohydrodynamics equations in complex form (FI-CMHD), a complete set of field equations for the real values potentials $\Theta(z, \bar{z})$, $\Phi(z, \bar{z})$ the complex velocity \mathbf{u} , and the complex magnetic field \mathbf{B} . For the full imaginary plane they are not necessary boundary conditions. These equations are connected thanks to the product of both fields $\mathbf{u}\mathbf{B}$, in the magnetic equation, and thanks to the square of magnetic fields \mathbf{B}^2 in the velocity equation (2.13).

3. A family of particular solutions

The central idea is to try to find a family of solutions for these equations, thanks to the decoupling of the fluid equation and magnetic equation. In (3.5) we find the solutions:

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{Re}{Rm} \mathbf{u}, \quad (3.1)$$

then for the following relation of dimensionless numbers:

$$\frac{SR_e}{R_m} = 1, \quad (3.2)$$

the equations (2.13) are transformed into the equations (3.5), if the second derivative of velocity potential is express like this:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} = - \frac{\frac{\partial F(z)}{\partial z}}{R_e^2 (F(z) - z)^2}, \quad (3.3)$$

and the second derivative of the magnetic potential like this:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial z^2} = - \frac{\frac{\partial F(z)}{\partial z}}{R_m^2 (F(z) - z)^2}, \quad (3.4)$$

then the equations (3.5) appear as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} -\frac{iF(z)'}{R_e(F(z)-z)^2} - i\mathbf{u}^2 &= \frac{1}{R_e} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial z}, \\ -\frac{iF(z)'}{R_m(F(z)-z)^2} - i\mathbf{B}^2 &= \frac{1}{R_m} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial z}, \\ \Im\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \bar{z}}\right) &= 0, \\ \Im\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \bar{z}}\right) &= 0, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.5)$$

Thus, a family of solutions exist for these equations which disconnect the velocity field, and we can write them in the following form:

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \frac{R_m}{R_e} \mathbf{B}^* = \frac{i}{R_e(F(z)-z)}, \quad (3.6)$$

where (3.6) is a solution for the velocity and magnetic equations of (3.5), for an abundant family of $F(z)$. It is not difficult to demonstrate of this affirmation. Here we have some examples of solutions for the complex Navier-Stokes equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}^* &= \frac{-i}{R_e z}, \\ \mathbf{u}^* &= \frac{-isenz}{R_e}, \\ \mathbf{u}^* &= \frac{i}{R_e z(z-1)}, \\ \mathbf{u}^* &= -\frac{i}{R_e z^n}, \\ \mathbf{u}^* &= \frac{i}{R_e} \left(z + \frac{1}{z}\right), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.7)$$

This means that the magnetic and velocity solutions (3.6) are the same, i.e. except for a dimensionless multiplicative factor. The magnetic potential:

$$\Theta = -\frac{1}{R_m^2} \int \int \frac{dF}{(F(z)-z)^2} dz + p_1(\bar{z})z + p_2(\bar{z}), \quad (3.8)$$

and the velocity potential:

$$\Phi = -\frac{1}{R_e^2} \int \int \frac{dF}{(F(z)-z)^2} dz + q_1(\bar{z})z + q_2(\bar{z}), \quad (3.9)$$

This second anti-derivatives must be chosen carefully because the potential $(\Phi(z, \bar{z}), \Theta(z, \bar{z}))$ must fulfill:

$$\Phi, \Theta : \mathbb{C} \times \mathbb{C} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (3.10)$$

The solutions (3.6) satisfy the (3.5) equations, with the potentials (3.9) and (3.8). When the inviscid flow is irrotational the term: $\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \bar{z} \partial z} = S(\overline{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{B})$ complement Bernoulli's equation. Then $\frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial \bar{z} \partial z} = C(\bar{z}) = \text{constant}$. The fluid will satisfy the Bernoulli equation or not, being kept viscous in both cases. This is a new aspect that appears as result of taking things to the complex plane, where there are viscous fluids that meet the complex Bernoulli equation. The found solution keeps this validity for a region in the parameter space where the triple product remains equal to unity.

3.1. $R_e = R_m$

From the equations (2.13) when $R_m = R_e$ another way exist to decouple. By summing and subtracting both equations in (2.13) and multiplying the second equation by $S^{\frac{1}{2}}$ we obtain:

$$i\left(\frac{\partial\Phi^2}{\partial z^2} \pm \sqrt{S}\frac{\partial^2\Theta}{\partial z^2}\right) - \frac{i}{2}(\mathbf{u}^2 \pm 2\sqrt{S}\mathbf{u}\mathbf{B} + S\mathbf{B}^2) = \frac{1}{R_e}\left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{u}}{\partial z} \pm \sqrt{S}\frac{\partial\mathbf{B}}{\partial z}\right), \quad (3.11)$$

this is equivalent to:

$$i\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}(\Phi \pm \sqrt{S}\Theta) - \frac{i}{2}(\mathbf{u} \pm \sqrt{S}\mathbf{B})^2 = \frac{1}{R_e}\frac{\partial}{\partial z}(\mathbf{u} \pm \sqrt{S}\mathbf{B}), \quad (3.12)$$

if introducing:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Phi_1 &= \Phi + \sqrt{S}\Theta, \\ \Phi_2 &= \Phi - \sqrt{S}\Theta, \\ \mathbf{u}_1 &= \mathbf{u} + \sqrt{S}\mathbf{B}, \\ \mathbf{u}_2 &= \mathbf{u} - \sqrt{S}\mathbf{B}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.13)$$

then the following system of equations is obtained:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} i\frac{\partial^2\Phi_1}{\partial z^2} - \frac{i}{2}\mathbf{u}_1^2 &= \frac{1}{R_e}\frac{\partial\mathbf{u}_1}{\partial z}, \\ i\frac{\partial^2\Phi_2}{\partial z^2} - \frac{i}{2}\mathbf{u}_2^2 &= \frac{1}{R_e}\frac{\partial\mathbf{u}_2}{\partial z}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.14)$$

this system (3.14) is decoupled and every equation is solved separately. Both are Navier-Stokes type equations in complex form (Scholle *et al.* 2010). If the originals solutions \mathbf{u}_1, Φ_1 and \mathbf{u}_2, Φ_2 are found, then \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{B} are found as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u}_1 + \mathbf{u}_2), \\ \mathbf{B} &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{S}}(\mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbf{u}_2), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.15)$$

4. Conclusion

The complex variable formulation for two-dimensional viscous flow and electrically conducting fluid with two new scalars (Φ and Θ), i.e. for the MHD equations, allows this problem, in \mathbb{R}^2 , to be successfully brought to the complex plane \mathbb{C} . This first integral complex equation is particular because it opens a new range of complex solutions for an old problem, which is not necessarily rich in quadrature solutions. The applicability of this situation is not so clear, but from the theoretical point of view some benefits seem to be evident, both in the examination of the dynamic and stability, or other problems in fluid dynamics.

A problem that remains open is related to the three-dimensional case (\mathbb{R}^3), which is to find a way of taking the set of connected equations (MHD) to arrival at an abundance of solutions. How to attempt this is not trivial, because we do not know the manifold in which to put this wonderful set of equations. We think that they could open new ways to study FI-MHD equations. But apparently certain difficulties interfere in this paradigm, the majority associated with the treatment of the vectorial operators ($\nabla(\ast)$, $\nabla \cdot$

$(*)$, $\nabla^2(*)$, $\nabla \times (*)$ in \mathbb{R}^3 and at the same time encounter a complex representation. As of yet, we do not know how address those challenges.

REFERENCES

- DAVISON, P. A. 2001 An introduction to magnetohydrodynamics. *Cambridge texts in applied mathematics, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, 1. publ. edition* .
- LIU, L. Q., WU, J. Z., SHI, Y. P. & ZHU, J. Y. 2014 A dynamic counterpart of lamb vector in viscous compressible aerodynamics. *Fluid Dyn. Res.* **46**, 061417.
- MAN, Y K 1994 First integrals of autonomous systems of differential equations and the Prolle-Singer procedure. *J. Phys. A:Math.Gen.* **27** (Printed in UK), L329–L332.
- SCHOLLE, M., HAAS, A. H. & GASKELL, P. H. 2010 A first integral of navier-stokes equations and its applications. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond.* **467**, 127–143.
- SERMANGE, M. & TEMAM, R. 1983 Some mathematical questions related to the mhd equations. *RR-0185, INRIA. 1983.* <inria-00076373> .
- SPIEGEL, M. R. 1972 Variáveis complexas. In *Complex variables* (ed. McGraw-Hill Book Co), *Schaum*, vol. 218, pp. 102–105. McGraw-Hill do Brasil.